

ISic1666

I.Sicily inscription 3338

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

ash chest

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

2016-06-27

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

First recorded by Orsi in 1889, among material of uncertain provenance located in the museum stores and not recorded in CIL

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 50198

Physical Description

A white limestone ash chest (no lid preserved), plain on all sides except the front, which has an incised border and incised diagonals crossing the face (and which appear to precede the inscribed letters which they traverse).

Dimensions

Height 25 cm

Width 43 cm

Depth 41 cm

Layout

Latin text, aligned to the left margin over two lines, with guidelines (no interlinear spacing)

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Somewhat irregularly spaced tall letters, with thin strokes but pronounced terminations to the strokes. A has a detached downward descending middle-bar; E is tall thin, with shorter top bar; G is formed as a C with the tail a second short curving stroke; P is closed; R has small eye, slightly open; S leans forward slightly. The use of interpuncts is erratic and seemingly not linked to sense, with a triangular punct after the initial A and at the end of line 2; a large reversed comma-shape midline after the R of line 1; and a smaller comma-shape mid-line between V and R in line 2.

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 0 mm

Text

1. A·per · (vac.undefin)

2. Augu·rinus ·

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Aper Augurinus

Commentary

Although the text was recorded by Orsi in NSA for 1889 (and picked up from there in EphEp VIII) as being among the objects in the museum stores missed by CIL, it does not appear to have been added to the inventory until c.1946. The mixed use of interpuncts is curious and appears to bear little relation to the words. The punct after the A might suggest the praenomen A(ulus), but in that case the vacat after 'per' implies the omission of the rest of the nomen (? Perpenna?) from the inscription, with Augurinus as the cognomen. The alternative is to read simply 'Aper', which although rare is attested as a name.

Digital identifiers:

TM 492382

EDCS 34700070

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-

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Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 687

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014